

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Exploration of CCD-Number for Some Specific Graphs

G Mahadevan^{1*}, K Priya¹, C Sivagnanam²

¹ Department of Mathematics, The Gandhigram Rural Institute - Deemed to be University, Gandhigram, Tamil Nadu, India

² Mathematics and Computing Skills Unit, Sur, Sultanate of Oman

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 29-08-2023

Accepted: 05-03-2024

Published: 31-05-2024

Editor: ICDMMMDE-2023 Special Issue Editors: Dr. G. Mahadevan & Prof. Dr. P. Balasubramaniam

Citation: Mahadevan G, Priya K, Sivagnanam C (2024) Exploration of CCD-Number for Some Specific Graphs. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 17(SP1): 144-148. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17sp1.274>

* Corresponding author.
drgmaha2014@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2024 Mahadevan et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment (iSee)

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: A dominating set S of a graph G is said to be a complementary corona dominating set (CCD-set) if every vertex in $\langle V - S \rangle$ is either a pendent vertex or a support vertex. The smallest cardinality of a CCD-set is called the CCD-number and is denoted by $\gamma_{CCD}(G)$. In this article, we explore the CCD-number for some specific graphs. **Methods:** We are finding the upper bound of $\gamma_{CCD}(G)$ and the lower bound of $\gamma_{CCD}(G)$. We prove that both the upper and lower bound are equal for the given graphs. **Findings:** In this article, we obtained the CCD-number for some specific graphs. **Novelty:** Complementary corona dominating set is a vertex set such that the induced subgraph of the complementary set is isomorphic to corona virus.

Keywords: Dominating Set; Corona Dominating Set; Support And Pendent Vertex; Butterfly Graph; Dumbbell Graph; Coconut Tree Graph; Peacock Head Graph; Sunlet Graph; Spider Graph; Firecracker Graph; Uniform g-ply graph

1 Introduction

This study considers a simple undirected graph with no loops or multiple edges. Typically V and E stand for the number of vertices and edges in a graph G respectively. A graph vertex's degree is determined by counting the number of edges that incident on it, twice accounting for loops. The notation $\deg(v)$ represents a vertex v degree. A graphs maximum and minimum degrees are indicated by the symbols $\Delta(G)$ and $\delta(G)$, respectively. G. Mahadevan et al. ⁽¹⁾ proposed the idea of corona domination in graphs and L. Praveen Kumar et al. ⁽²⁾ introduced the idea of CD-number of graphs. S. Anuthiya et al ⁽³⁾ introduced the concept for exploration of CPCD Number for power graph. M. Vimala Suganthi et al ⁽⁴⁾ motivated by this paper CCD-number of a graphs.

A butterfly graph $BF_{s,g}$ ⁽⁵⁾ two even C_g of the same order with s pendent edge attaching common vertex. The graph joining two disjoint cycles $(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_g, x_1)$ and $(y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_g, y_1)$ by an edge $x_1 y_1$ is called dumbbell graph ⁽⁶⁾ and it is denoted by Db_g . The coconut tree ⁽⁷⁾ is created by joining s pendant edges to an end vertex of a path called P_g . It is denoted by $CT_{g,s}$. The peacock head graph is a graph obtained from $C_g = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_g, x_1)$ by attaching y pendent edges to a vertex x_1 of C_g and it is denoted by $PC_{g,s}$. The sunlet graph ⁽⁸⁾ S_g is a cycle C_g attaching a pendant vertices. The spider graph $S(g, s)$ ⁽⁹⁾ is obtained from $K_{1,s}$ by pasting an end vertex of P_g to each pendant of $K_{1,s}$. A (g, k) -firecracker graph ⁽¹⁰⁾ $P_g = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_g)$ by combining

the root vertex of k-star [star graph with k vertices] to $x_i; 1 \leq i \leq g$ by an edge denoted by $F_{g,k}$. A uniform g-ply graph is obtained from r distinct paths $P_s, s \geq 3$ by joining all the initial vertices to a new vertex u by an edge and all the terminal vertices to a new vertex v by an edge and is denoted by $P_g(s)$.

2 Methodology

In this paper we are finding the exact value of exploration of CCD-number for some specific graphs. We prove the upper and lower bound of the parameter for the given graphs.

3 Result and Discussion

Theorem:3.1

If $g \geq 4$, then

$$\gamma_{CCD}(BF_{s,g}) = \begin{cases} 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s - 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let $V(BF_{s,g}) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_g, v'_1, v'_2, \dots, v'_g, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_s\}$ and

$$E(BF_{s,g}) = (v_i v_{i+1} ; v'_i v'_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq g - 1) \cup (v_1 v_g, v'_1 v'_g) \cup \{v_1 w_i : 1 \leq i \leq s\},$$

$v_1 = v'_1$ be the common vertex. Let $A = \{v_i, v'_i : i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}\} \cup \{w_i : 1 \leq i \leq s\}$.

Assume

$$S = \begin{cases} A & \text{if } g = 3q \text{ or } 3q + 1 \\ A \cup \{v_g, v'_g\} & \text{if } g = 3q + 2 \end{cases}$$

Then S is a CCD-set of $BF_{s,g}$ and hence

$$\gamma_{CCD}(BF_{s,g}) \leq |S| = \begin{cases} 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s - 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most

$$k = \begin{cases} 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s - 2 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have

$$|D| \geq k + 1 = \begin{cases} 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s - 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Hence the Proof.

Theorem:3.2

If $g \geq 3$, then

$$\gamma_{CCD}(Db_g) = \begin{cases} 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + 2 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let $V(Db_g) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_g, v'_1, v'_2, \dots, v'_g\}$ and $E(Db_g) = (v_i v_{i+1}, v'_i v'_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq g - 1) \cup (v_1 v_g, v'_1 v'_g) \cup \{v_1 v'_1\}$. Let $A = \{v_i, v'_i : i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}\}$.

Assume

$$S = \begin{cases} A & \text{if } g = 3q \text{ or } 3q + 1 \\ A \cup \{v_g, v'_g\} & \text{if } g \equiv 3q + 2 \end{cases}$$

Then S is a CCD-set of Db_g and hence

$$\gamma_{CCD}(Db_g) \leq |S| = \begin{cases} 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + 2 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most $k = \begin{cases} 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil - 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \left\lceil \frac{g}{3} \right\rceil + 1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$

contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have

$$|D| \geq k + 1 = \begin{cases} 2 \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ 2 \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + 2 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Hence the Proof.

Theorem:3.3

If $g \geq 2$, then

$$\gamma_{CCD}(CT_{g,s}) = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof:

Let $V(CT_{g,s}) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_g, v'_1, v'_2, \dots, v'_s\}$ and $E(CT_{g,s}) = (v_i v_{i+1}) : 1 \leq i \leq g - 1 \cup \{v_g v'_i : 1 \leq i \leq s\}$. Let $A = (v_i : i = 3q + 1) \cup \{v'_i : 1 \leq i \leq s\}$.

Assume

$$S = \begin{cases} A & \text{if } g = 3q \text{ or } 3q + 1 \\ A \cup \{v_g\} & \text{if } g \equiv 3q + 2 \end{cases}$$

Then S is a CCD-set of $CT_{g,s}$ and hence

$$\gamma_{CCD}(CT_{g,s}) \leq |S| = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most $k = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s - 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have

$$|D| \geq k + 1 = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Hence the Proof .

Theorem:3.4

If $g \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{CCD}(PC_{g,s}) = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Proof:

Let $V(PC_{g,s}) = (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_g, v'_1, v'_2, v'_3, \dots, v'_s)$ and $E(PC_{g,s}) = (v_i v_{i+1}), v_1 v_g v_1 v'_j : 1 \leq i \leq g - 1; 1 \leq j \leq s\}$. Let $A = (v_i : i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}) \cup \{v'_i : 1 \leq i \leq s\}$.

Assume $S = \begin{cases} A & \text{if } g = 3q \text{ or } 3q + 1 \\ A \cup \{v_{g-1}\} & \text{if } g = 3q + 2 \end{cases}$

Then S is a CCD-set of $PC_{g,s}$ and hence

$$\gamma_{CCD}(PC_{g,s}) \leq |S| = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most

$$k = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s - 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have

$$|D| \geq k + 1 = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Hence the Proof.

Theorem:3.5

If $g \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{CCD}(S_g) = \lceil \frac{g}{5} \rceil + g$.

Proof:

Let $E(S_g) = \{v_i v_{i+1}, v_1 v_g, v_j v'_j : 1 \leq i \leq g-1, 1 \leq j \leq g\}$. and $E(S_g) = \{v_i v_{i+1}, v_1 v_g, v_j v'_j : 1 \leq i \leq g-1, 1 \leq j \leq g\}$. Let $A = \{v_i : i \equiv 1 \pmod{5}\} \cup \{v'_i : 1 \leq i \leq r\}$.

Assume $S = \begin{cases} A - \{v_{g-1}\} \cup \{v_{g-2}\} & \text{if } g \equiv 2 \pmod{5} \\ A & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Then S is a CCD-set of S_g and hence $\gamma_{CCD}(S_g) \leq |S| = \lceil \frac{g}{5} \rceil 5 + g$.

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most $k = \lceil \frac{g}{5} \rceil + g - 1$, contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have $|D| \geq k + 1 = \lceil \frac{g}{5} \rceil + g$.

Hence the Proof.

Theorem:3.6

If $g \geq 2$ and $s \geq 3$ then $\gamma_{CCD}(S(g,s)) = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s + 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Proof:

Let $V(S(g,s)) = \{u, x^i_1, x^i_2, x^i_3, \dots, x^i_g : 1 \leq i \leq s\}$ and $E(S(g,s)) = \{ux^i_1 : 1 \leq i \leq s\} \cup \{x^i_j x^i_{j+1} : 1 \leq i \leq s; 1 \leq j \leq g-1\}$. Let $A = \{x^i_j : j \equiv 0 \pmod{3} : 1 \leq i \leq s\} \cup \{u\}$.

Assume $S = \begin{cases} A & \text{if } g = 3q \\ A \cup \{x^i_g : 1 \leq i \leq s\} & \text{if } g \equiv 3q + 1 \\ A \cup \{x^i_{g-1}, x^i_g : 1 \leq i \leq s\} & \text{if } g \equiv 3q + 2 \end{cases}$

Then S is a CCD-set of $S(g,s)$ and hence

$\gamma_{CCD}(S(g,s)) \leq |S| = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s + 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s + s + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most $k = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s + s & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have

$|D| \geq k + 1 = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s + 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil s + s + 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Hence the Proof.

Theorem:3.7

If $g \geq 2$ then $\gamma_{CCD}(F_{g,k}) = \begin{cases} 2 \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil + (k-1)g + 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil + (k-1)g & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Proof:

Let $V(F_{g,k}) = \{x'_1, x'_2, \dots, x'_g, y^i_1, y^i_2, \dots, y^i_k : 1 \leq i \leq g\}$ and $E(F_{g,k}) = \{x'_i x'_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq g-1\} \cup \{x'_i y^i_1 : 1 \leq i \leq g\} \cup \{y^i_1 y^i_j : 1 \leq i \leq g; 2 \leq j \leq k\}$. Let $A = \{x'_i, y^i_1 : i = 3q + 2\} \cup \{y^i_j : 1 \leq i \leq g; 1 \leq j \leq k\}$.

Assume $S = \begin{cases} A & \text{if } g = 3q \text{ or } 3q + 2 \\ A \cup \{y^g_1\} & \text{if } g \equiv 3q + 1. \end{cases}$

Then S is a CCD-set of $F_{g,k}$ and hence

$\gamma_{CCD}(F_{g,k}) \leq |S| = \begin{cases} 2 \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil + (k-1)g + 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil + (k-1)g & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most

$k = \begin{cases} 2 \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil + (k-1)g & \text{if } g \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lceil \frac{g}{3} \rceil + (k-1)g - 1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$

contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have

$$|D| \geq k + 1 = \begin{cases} 2 \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + (k - 1)g + 1 & \text{if } g \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{g}{3} \rfloor + (k - 1)g & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Hence the Proof.

Theorem:3.8

If $g \geq 2$ then $\gamma_{CCD}(P_g(s)) = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 2 & \text{if } s \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Proof:

Let $V(P_g(s)) = \{u, v, x_1^i, x_2^i, \dots, x_s^i\}$ and $E(P_g(s)) = \{x_j^i x_{j+1}^i : 1 \leq i \leq g; 1 \leq j \leq s - 1\} \cup \{ux_1^i, vx_s^i : 1 \leq i \leq g\}$. Let $A = \{x_j^i : j = 3q : 1 \leq i \leq g\}$.

Assume $S = \begin{cases} A \cup \{u, v\} & \text{if } s = 3q \text{ or } 3q + 2 \\ A \cup \{u\} \cup \{x_s^1\} & \text{if } s \equiv 3q + 1 \end{cases}$

Then S is a CCD-set of $P_g(s)$ and hence $\gamma_{CCD}(P_g(s)) \leq |S| = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 2 & \text{if } s \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Since any dominating set D of cardinality at most $k = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 1 & \text{if } s \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

contains at least one isolated vertex in $\langle V - D \rangle$, we have

$$|D| \geq k + 1 = \begin{cases} \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 2 & \text{if } s \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \\ \lfloor \frac{s}{3} \rfloor g + 2 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Hence the Proof.

4 Conclusion

Throughout in this article, we found the CCD-number for $BF_{s,g}, Db_g, CT_{g,s}, PC_{g,s}, S_g, S_{g,s}, F_{g,k}$ and $P_g(s)$. For the future work, we extend this parameter for trees, product related graphs, power graphs and comparing other parameter which will be prove the subsequent papers.

Declaration

Presented in 9th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DISCRETE MATHEMATICS AND MATHEMATICAL MODELLING IN DIGITAL ERA (ICDMMMDE-2023) during March 23-25, 2023, Organized by the Department of Mathematics, The Gandhigram Rural Institute (Deemed to be University), Gandhigram - 624302, Dindigul, Tamil Nadu, India. ICDMMMDE-23 was supported by GRI-DTBU, CSIR.

References

- 1) Mahadevan G, Sugathi V, Sivagnana M. Corona Domination Number of graphs. *International conference on mathematical Modelling and Computational Intelligence Techniques*. 2021;376:255–265. Available from: <http://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-6018-4>.
- 2) Praveenkumar L, Mahadevan G, Sivagnanam C. An Investigation of Corona Domination Number for Some Special Graphs and Jahangir Graph. *Baghdad Science Journal*. 2023;20(1(SI)):294–299. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21123/bsj.2023.8416>.
- 3) Anuthiya S, Mahadevan G, Sivagnanam C. Exploration of CPCD number for power graph. *Baghdad Science Journal*. 2023;20(1(SI)):0380–0380. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21123/bsj.2023.8423>.
- 4) Suganthi MV. Innovation of a Systematic Analysis of Various Domination Parameters with Applications. *The Gandhigram Rural Institute*.
- 5) Shalaan MM, Omran AA. Co-Even Domination Number in Some Graphs. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. 2020;928(4):042015–042015. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1757-899x/928/4/042015>.
- 6) Gipson KL, Kalaiarasan KSJ. Eccentric domination path decomposition of Dumbbell graph. *International journal of health sciences*. 2022;6(S2):2855–2860. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS2.5797>.
- 7) Maheswari V, Kiruthika NHA, Nagarajan A. On 2-Domination Number of Some Graphs. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 2021;1947(1):012001–012001. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1947/1/012001>.
- 8) Vijayalekshmi A, Prabha AE. Introduction of color class dominating sets in graphs. *Malaya Journal of Matematik*. 2020;8(4):2186–2189. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.26637/mjm0804/0146>.
- 9) Varghese S, Varghese S, Vijayakumar A. Power domination in Mycielskian of spiders. *AKCE International Journal of Graphs and Combinatorics*. 2022;19(2):154–158. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09728600.2022.2082900>.
- 10) Vijayalekshmi, Niju. Dominator color class dominating sets on fire cracker, gear and flower graphs. *Malaya Journal of Matematik*;9(1):1043–1046. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.26637/MJM0901/0183>.